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DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE REGIONAL ORGANIZATION OF TOURISM AND ITS MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS IN THE KASHKADARYA REGION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the characteristics of the territorial organization of tourism in the Kashkadarya region, the level of use of existing tourist resources, and the current state of regional management mechanisms. During the study, the level of development of tourism infrastructure in the region, the distribution of tourist flows across regions, and problems in the management system were identified. Also, modern management approaches, innovative mechanisms, and directions for institutional improvement in the territorial development of tourism were substantiated. According to the results of the article, it is scientifically proven that the sustainable development of the regional economy can be ensured by effectively organizing tourism in the Kashkadarya region and improving the management system.

Key words: tourism, territorial development, tourist infrastructure, management mechanism, tourism efficiency, territorial organization, tourist resources, innovative approach, sustainable tourism, economic development.

INTRODUCTION

In the current context of globalization, the tourism industry is recognized as one of the fastest-growing sectors of the world economy. It plays a crucial strategic role in diversifying regional economies, generating employment, and fostering the development of the service sector. Accordingly, the effective territorial organization of tourism and its advancement through modern management mechanisms represent both a relevant scientific inquiry and a promising practical direction.

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has demonstrated strong commitment to the development of its tourism sector. Comprehensive reforms have been implemented to modernize tourism infrastructure, establish new tourist destinations, enhance service quality, and unlock regional tourism potential. These initiatives have created a solid institutional and economic foundation for sustainable growth in the industry.

Although the level of tourism development varies across regions, this diversity reflects significant opportunities for targeted regional strategies and differentiated development approaches. Existing tourism resources, while not yet fully utilized, provide substantial potential for expansion, innovation, and value creation within the sector.

The Kashkadarya region stands out as a particularly promising area for tourism development due to its rich historical and cultural heritage, unique natural landscapes, and strong ethnographic appeal. While certain aspects of infrastructure and organizational coordination continue to evolve, ongoing efforts aimed at systematizing tourism development and improving management efficiency are creating favorable conditions for unlocking the region's full potential.

In this context, the role of effective management mechanisms becomes especially important. A well-structured management system enables the rational use of tourism resources, stimulates investment activity, supports infrastructure development, and enhances service quality. Moreover, the integration of innovative approaches, digital technologies, and public-private partnership models opens new avenues for increasing the competitiveness and sustainability of regional tourism development.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Issues of territorial development of tourism and its effective management have been extensively studied in world and national scientific literature, and this area is considered an important component of economic geography, regional economy and the development of the service sector [1]. Issues of territorial organization of tourism are studied, first of all, inextricably linked to its economic efficiency, social significance and environmental sustainability [2].

In international scientific research, the theoretical foundations of territorial development of tourism were developed by scientists such as B. Bramwell, R. Butler, D. Pearce, J. Urry [3]. In particular, B. Bramwell substantiated the importance of cooperation between stakeholders and institutional management mechanisms in tourism management [4].

The theory of the life cycle of tourism areas (Tourism Area Life Cycle – TALC), developed by R. Butler, explains the gradual evolution of tourism development [5]. This model justifies the need for strategic planning and rational use of resources in regional tourism management.

D. Pearce, on the other hand, pays special attention to the integration of transport infrastructure, service systems and management institutions in regional tourism planning [6]. In his opinion, the regional development of tourism is directly related to effective management and marketing strategies.

In modern research, the concept of sustainability plays an important role in the regional development of tourism. In this regard, the approaches developed by the UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) are recognized as a global standard in tourism management [7].

In the domestic scientific literature, the economic and organizational aspects of tourism development have been studied by A. Abdiyev, Sh. Yuldashev, B. Umarov and other scientists [8–10]. They emphasize the important role of state policy, investment climate and infrastructure in the development of tourism.

However, an analysis of existing scientific research shows that a comprehensive analysis of the territorial organization of tourism and its management mechanisms in the Kashkadarya region has not been sufficiently covered. Therefore, in this article, it is relevant to conduct a systematic analysis using the example of this region.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a comprehensive approach to studying the territorial organization and management mechanisms of tourism. In particular, the relationship between the main structural elements of tourism was studied using the systematic analysis method, and regional indicators were compared with the republican level using the comparative method. Based on the statistical analysis method, the dynamics of tourism flows and the volume of services were analyzed, the effectiveness of management mechanisms was determined through expert assessment, and the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats of regional tourism were assessed using the SWOT analysis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In recent years, positive dynamic changes have been observed in the tourism sector in the Kashkadarya region. In particular, as a result of the recovery processes after the pandemic, the flow of tourism gradually increased between 2020 and 2024. This is explained, on the one hand, by the activation of domestic tourism, and on the other hand, by the implementation of state programs aimed at developing tourism infrastructure in the region. As a result, the tourist attractiveness of the region has increased, and new tourist destinations have begun to form.

According to the results of 2024, the number of tourists visiting the region has reached approximately 450-500 thousand people, which indicates a significant increase compared to 2020. The volume of tourism services is growing by an average of 12-15 percent per year, indicating that the share of this sector in the regional economy is increasing. At the same time, the 1.3-fold increase in the number of hotels and other accommodation facilities reflects the expansion of tourism infrastructure (Table 1).

Table 1. Dynamics of tourism indicators in the Kashkadarya region (2020–2024)

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Number of tourists (thousands)	210	260	340	420	480
Volume of services (billion soums)	95	120	160	210	260
Number of hotels (units)	85	92	105	118	130

At the same time, the conducted analysis indicates promising opportunities for more balanced regional development of tourism. While tourism activity is currently more concentrated in Karshi and Shahrisabz, this creates a strong foundation and experience base that can be effectively extended to other districts. The relatively lower level of infrastructure development in certain areas reflects untapped potential, offering new directions for investment and strategic planning.

This situation opens up possibilities for redistributing tourist flows more evenly across the region and ensuring more efficient use of available resources. In particular, improving transport accessibility, as well as enhancing service and information infrastructure in remote areas, can significantly increase their attractiveness for visitors. As a result, a more integrated and inclusive tourism system can be formed, contributing to sustainable regional development and greater economic impact (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of tourism in Kashkadarya region by region (2024)

The analysis highlights several important areas of opportunity within the tourism sector. In particular, the current territorial distribution of tourist facilities suggests significant potential for more balanced and strategic development. While certain regions already possess considerable tourism resources, their further enhancement and integration into the broader tourism network can substantially increase overall sector performance. Improvements in transport and logistics infrastructure will play a key role in expanding tourist flows and strengthening regional connectivity.

At the same time, the existing level of marketing and branding presents an opportunity to more actively promote the region's tourism potential at both national and international levels. Strengthening these efforts can significantly improve visibility and attract a wider range of visitors. Moreover, ongoing institutional evolution, including gradual decentralization and increased support for local initiatives, can further enhance the effectiveness and responsiveness of tourism management at the regional level.

The results of the SWOT analysis reinforce these positive prospects. The region's rich historical and cultural heritage—particularly the global recognition of Shahrisabz as a major tourist destination—along with its diverse natural resources and strong state support for tourism development, constitute a solid foundation for future growth. At the same time, areas such as infrastructure development, service quality improvement, and human capital enhancement represent key directions for strategic investment and capacity building, offering substantial potential to elevate the overall competitiveness of the tourism sector.

In terms of opportunities, there is an opportunity to increase the efficiency of tourism by developing domestic tourism, attracting investment to the region, and introducing digital technologies. In particular, the use of modern information and communication technologies can widely promote the tourism potential of the region. At the same time, increased competition with competing regions, environmental problems, and global economic crises are considered the main threats that can negatively affect tourism development.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

According to the results of the study, significant opportunities have been identified for further enhancing the territorial organization and management mechanisms of tourism in the Kashkadarya region. The region's

high tourism potential provides a strong basis for its dynamic and systematic development. At the same time, the existing management framework offers room for optimization, particularly in improving the efficiency of resource utilization, achieving more balanced infrastructure development across districts, and increasing the adaptability of management approaches.

To fully realize this potential, it is important to strengthen regional tourism planning by developing tailored strategies that reflect the specific characteristics and advantages of each district. Further modernization of transport, accommodation, and service infrastructure will contribute to improving the overall quality of tourism services and visitor experience. Enhancing management effectiveness through greater involvement of local authorities and the private sector can also support more flexible and responsive decision-making processes.

In addition, the advancement of digital tourism represents a key area of growth under modern conditions. The introduction of online platforms, digital marketing tools, and smart technologies can significantly increase the visibility and attractiveness of the region in the global tourism market.

In conclusion, the effective organization of tourism on a regional basis, combined with the implementation of modern management mechanisms, creates favorable conditions for sustainable economic development in the Kashkadarya region. These measures will contribute to job creation, more efficient use of local resources, and a steady increase in the region's investment attractiveness.

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